

STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AS INFLUENCED BY TEACHERS' QUALITY: EVIDENCE FROM SOUTHWEST, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

Secondary educational system in Nigeria has been experiencing serious backwardness because of poor teachers' quality (TQ) which consequently leads to low students' academic achievement (SAA). This study aimed at investigating the relationship between teachers' quality, and students' academic achievement in Yewa South Local Government Area (YSLGA) of Ogun State. A cumulative total of 2550 respondents (including 15 subject teachers from the senior secondary and the heads per school in 15 schools covering 10 wards) were selected. The respondents were selected from 15 randomly selected public and private senior secondary schools in YSLGA, Ogun State, Nigeria between 2016 and 2018. Two researcher-designed instruments, namely; Teachers' Quality Assessment Questionnaire (TQAQ), and Students' Academic Performance Proforma (SAPP), were used to collect relevant data for the study. The instruments were validated by some experts in Educational Management, Measurement, Evaluation and Statistics. The coefficients of reliability of TQAQ after a two-week test-retest were found to be 0.75. Eighteen research questions and hypotheses were formulated and tested. Means, Weighted means and Percentage were used to answer the research questions raised. Regression analysis was used to test the main hypothesis. In addition, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Statistical Method was used to test the operational hypotheses, all at 0.05 significance level using XLSTAT and SPSS statistical tools. The correlation between TQ and SAA was positively strong ($R^2 = 925$). At 0.05 level of confidence, the regression analysis showed significant relationship between TQ and SAA ($p > 0.001$). This finding showed that teachers' quality especially years of teaching experience strongly influenced students' academic achievement. The study recommends that school proprietors and the government through the inspectorate division must routinely visit schools to ensure that teachers are qualified

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and are properly discharging their primary assignment to enhance students' academic achievement.

Keywords: teachers' quality, teachers' education, secondary school, academic achievement, Nigeria

1. Introduction

The concept of quality in the educational system is contemporarily getting a reasonable attention in the human affairs. Parents, guardians and the entire society have been campaigning for quality education (Nwogbo, 2007). The quest and necessity for quality in education is not indifferent regarding the huge sum of cash channeled into the system. Madumere-Obike (2003) was of the opinion that education usurps reasonable part of public revenue. Thus, it is pertinent to note that those who manage schools should be accountable to the stakeholders. The quality of the products of education is an integral of such accountability.

Secondary education is a very critical level of any educational system because it is the foundation on which higher education is established as well as the basis for the academic development of any child. It is sad to note that the academic performance of students at this level is very poor in the study area. Several factors might be held responsible including high dependent on poor condition of service for teachers, low teachers' quality, inadequate teaching and learning facilities. These have adverse effects on the quality of teachers as well as the quality of instruction because no educational system can rise above the quality of its teachers (FRN, 2004).

The teacher is the pivot of the education process. The teacher is the key in the entire education programme and s/he can make or mar the best educational programme in the world. Education therefore is what teachers make of it. Thus, competent, devoted and professionally qualified teachers are essential foundation for a good education system. In other words, the attainment of national objectives for the adequate preparation of students for their examinations and achievement of educational objectives depend largely on teachers. Obemeata (1996) reported Pope Pius XII (1942) as having stated that:

"Good schools are the fruits not only of good regulations but primarily of good teachers excellently trained in their respective subjects which they are to teach and possessing the intellectual and moral qualities which their important offices require (p. 56)".

The above assertion implies that if teachers are to satisfactorily deliver their services and duties as expected of them, they should be of the right caliber as well as be adequately trained in order to be competent in the subjects which they are expected to teach.

1.1 Background to the Study

The study focuses on the randomly selected public and private secondary schools in Yewa South LGA (YSLGA) of Ogun State, Nigeria. The study area, Yewa South LGA (former Agbado South LGA) with headquarters in Ilaro is geographically located at 6°53'00"N and 3°01'00"E with an area of 629 km². Teachers' qualities in most secondary schools in YSLGA have been of crucial concern to majority of researchers in the field of educational administration and management. The teachers in YSLGA, Ogun State, and at large Nigeria's secondary schools are not only limited but are also professionally unqualified (Adebayo, 2007). Teachers should be able to introduce and apply various approaches in their teaching strategies, matching methods with contemporary scenarios and circumstances. Teachers ought to be thinking ahead about ways to enhance and improved teaching and learning processes. The non-availability of these services has adversely affected the quality of teachers in the schools. It has been observed that most teachers in the region are bent to be recycling old and outdated knowledge and practices in their respective subjects instead of reaching out for new innovations. The teachers need to upgrade their quality through higher academic qualifications, professional qualifications, and self-developments and experiences. In most cases, the teachers wait for the government to support their personal training instead of them 'taking the bull by the horn' as to enhance their teaching skills and methodologies for their students' excellence.

These constraints and other associated issues facing the schools in YSLGA raise doubt about the quality of teachers and students' academic achievements especially in the senior secondary schools, as well as the roles of the stakeholders in education (Nwogbo, 2007). It is therefore expedient to examine the different means whereby senior secondary school teachers can be kept abreast of time and thus improve their quality. In this context, this study examined the relationship among the teachers' quality, and students' academic achievement in public and private senior secondary schools in YSLGA of Ogun State, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Educational researchers have revealed that most secondary school leavers in Nigeria are poor in academic intelligence. Majority of them have pathetic results in both internal and external examinations. To determine school effectiveness, students' results in standardized tests, and their performance after school are the two variables which are usually employed.

In the recently released 2018 West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) results, less than 40% had five credits including Mathematics and English Language. This indicates that only very few secondary school leavers will have the qualification to be admitted into the tertiary (higher) educational institutions. Thus, most of these dropouts become nuisance and miscreants in the society. In as much as the teachers' quality is a crucial determinant of students' academic performance and fate after graduation, it is pertinent for the government and every stakeholder in education to support educational policies for students' excellence. This challenge has

been a serious issue of debate amongst the education administrators and researchers while considering which school parameters significantly influence students' achievement. The involvement of policymakers tends to have brought some reforms into the school system reform while, greater attention is given to the teacher quality in relation to students' achievement. These efforts seem not yielding positive results judging from the poor achievements from the school leavers. Consequently, a continuous outcry from educational platforms, parents, and guardians, about poor teaching and learning infrastructures was also noted.

Therefore, there is urgent need for teachers to know their onions by getting more academic and professional qualifications to impart the right knowledge to the students. Thus, the specific problem of this study encompasses investigating the degree to which teachers' quality influence students' academic achievement senior secondary schools in YSLGA of Ogun State, Nigeria.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the relationship among teachers' quality, and students' academic achievement in randomly selected public and private senior secondary schools in YSLGA of Ogun State, Nigeria.

Specifically, the objective of the study is to determine the influence of teachers' quality (including years of experience and academic qualifications) on students' academic achievement.

1.4 Significance of the Study

The challenges posed by the poor academic results among public senior secondary school students are critical issues that call for thorough and systematic investigations. It has been reported that students' academic achievement is highly influenced by teachers' quality than by the school's standard, school environment, race, class, or parents' socioeconomic status (Sanders, 1997). There have been several studies conducted in improving students' academic achievements but very little has been done focusing on teacher quality as principal factor. This study might optimistically provide some insight for educational planners and decision-makers by highlighting some basic clues which might have been apparently neglected by the stakeholders in educational management in YSLGA, Ogun State and Nigeria.

The findings of this study could contribute to existing literature by extending the stock of knowledge on the influence of teacher quality on students' performance in the secondary schools in YSLGA, Ogun State. Recommendations from the present study might positively assist teachers and school managers to re-examine the educational services that are available to them and identify the services which could promote quality teaching and learning. The research might further provide some useful reference materials for prospective researchers who could be probably interested in performing similar studies elsewhere. Additionally, the study emphasized that teachers should be academically, professionally, physically, mentally and intellectually qualified to be able to produce quality students towards sustainable economic development. The

study is expected to serve as a prime guide for teachers, educational planners and administrators on the necessity to improve the quality of secondary school teachers.

1.5 Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study was concerned with the relationship among teachers' quality, and students' academic achievement in public and private senior secondary schools, in YSLGA, Ogun State, Nigeria between 2016-2018.

1.6 Research Questions

This study answered the following research question:

- 1) What is the percentage of the teachers by academic and professional qualifications?
- 2) To what extent does teachers' qualification especially years of experience influence the students' academic achievement?

1.7 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses guided the study:

A. Main Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between teachers' quality, and students' academic achievements in senior secondary schools in YSLGA, Nigeria.

B. Operational Hypothesis

H0I: There is no significant relationship between teachers' years of experience and students' academic achievements in senior secondary schools, YSLGA, Nigeria.

1.8 Generic Definition of Terms

Academic intelligence: Means all the associated gain and achievement in terms of grades, certification, character, and expertise in one's given academic field.

Educational services: These are the services available for teachers to improve their quality and promote teachers' effectiveness in the school system. In this study, educational services are library services, in-service training, education resource services, information and communication technology (ICT) and educational supervision.

1.9 Operational Definition of Terms

Dependent variable: The dependent variable for this study is students' academic achievement.

Independent variables: The independent variables are teachers' quality.

Teacher quality: This means a degree of excellence, especially a high degree of goodness and worth of the teachers. In this study, teacher quality refers to teachers' academic qualification, professional qualification and years of experience.

Academic achievement: Examination result at the end of an academic programme in the school. In this study, the WASSCE result was applicable.

2. Methodology

This study investigated the relationship among teachers' quality, and students' academic achievements in public senior secondary schools in YSLGA, Nigeria. The teachers' quality is defined by the teachers' academic qualifications, teachers' professional qualifications, and years of teachers' teaching experiences. The following paragraphs described the steps employed in performing the study.

2.1 Research Design

The correlational survey design was used but it was conducted ex post facto. This was because the data were collected after the event had taken place, hence the name ex-post facto (Nworgu, 1991). It x-rayed the relationship among educational services, teacher quality and students' academic performance in North Central zone secondary schools. It was ex post facto because results of secondary school students in the sampled schools for the year 2015/2016, 2016/2017, and 2017/2018 were collected from the schools for the trends of academic achievements of the students.

2.2 Population, Sample and Sampling Techniques

The population consisted of the public senior secondary schools in YSLGA, Nigeria. Using a simple random sampling technique, 15 selected public and private senior secondary schools which were chosen from the political wards that made up of YSLGA, Ogun State. 10 public and 5 private senior secondary schools (at least a school per ward) were selected from each of the 10 wards in the LGA. Using proportional allocation method in stratified random sampling technique, the actual number of schools selected in each ward was taken. Furthermore, using proportional allocation method in stratified random sampling technique the actual number of teachers selected in each school was taken. A cumulative total of 2550 respondents (including 15 subject teachers for the senior secondary, the Principal and Vice-Principal=17 academic staff per school; 15 schools; 10 wards:17*15*10) were selected.

2.3 Research Instruments

In this study, two instruments were used. The first questionnaire was termed Teacher Quality Assessment Questionnaire (TQAQ) which was designed to measure the following sub-variables: teachers' academic qualifications, teachers' professional qualifications, and years of teachers' experience. And the second was the Students' Academic Performance Proforma (SAPP) which was used to collect the outcome from students' performance.

2.4 Validity and Reliability of Instruments

The purpose of validity is to determine the extent to which a research instrument measures what it is expected to measure. This was met through the following procedures:

After a thorough review of the relevant literature, the questionnaires were constructed and presented to an expert (who is a research assistant) for both face and content validity. In addition, copies of the questionnaires were distributed to some experts in Educational Management for judgement and criticism. This helped to assess the appropriateness of the questionnaire content and to determine content validity of the instrument. Furthermore, the construct validity was achieved through the painstaking efforts of experts in the Department of Measurement and Evaluation and Department of Statistics for the appropriateness of each item of the instrument.

Since tests cannot be valid unless it has high reliability, tests must therefore be consistent in the answers that they give. In this study, the test-retest method was used to determine the reliability of the questionnaires. The questionnaires were administered in 15 schools in YSLGA, Ogun State. A time lag of two weeks was given after the first test and then a retest of the instruments was administered again on the same respondents. The scores obtained during the first and second administration of the instruments on the test sample were correlated using correlation and regression analyses. The results obtained were 0.75 for Teacher Quality Assessment Questionnaire (TQAQ) at 0.05 level of significance. The research instruments were therefore considered reliable because of their high correlation co-efficient which Zimbardo (1997) considered as significant indication of reliability.

2.5 Administration of instrument/Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher, with the assistance of the experienced research assistants, visited all the selected secondary schools in the sampled wards for data collection. The wards were Ilaro I, Ilaro II, Ilaro III, Iwoye, Idogo, Owode I, Owode II, Ilobi/Erinja, Oke-Odan, and Ajilete. The three questionnaires were administered in each of the sampled schools. The Teacher Quality Assessment Questionnaires and the Student Academic Performance Proforma were completed by the 15 subjects' teachers for senior secondary, and Principal of each sampled school. The West African Examinations Council results of the students for three years: 2016-2018, on the subjects were also collected from the school principals to ascertain the trend of the academic performance of the students. The West African Senior School Certificate Examination is a standard examination and it is conducted not only for Nigerian students but also for students in other English-speaking West African countries such as Ghana and Gambia.

2.6 Methods of Data Analysis

The data collected for this study were analyzed using qualitative methods such as frequencies, mean and percentages for the descriptive data. The quantitative analysis used included simple regression analysis was used to test the main hypothesis involving three variables, while the correlation and regression analyses were used to test the operational hypotheses. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The West African Examination Council (WAEC) results of three years were collated and analyzed to show the trend of students' academic performance within the

stipulated period. And all the statistical analysis was performed using the XLSTAT and SPSS software packages.

3. Results and Discussions

Majority of the teachers in the study area have Nigerian Certificate of Education (NCE) (39.4%), and Ordinary National Diploma (OND) (16.6%), Postgraduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) (13.7%), Higher National Diploma (HND) (3.1%) whereas, less than 1% have PhD (Table 1, and Figure 1). This result was not surprise because Ph.D. holders are more relevant in higher institutions than in secondary schools and they often transfer to the tertiary educational sectors (Arinde, 2010). And contrary to the findings of Arinde (2010) in the North Central Nigeria, there were more NCE teachers in the public senior secondary schools in our study area.

Table 1: Summary of the highest Teachers' qualifications

Teacher quality	Total	%
NCE	1005	39.4
OND	424	16.6
HND	80	3.1
B.Ed	115	4.5
BSc/BA	403	15.8
PGDE	349	13.7
MSc/MA	66	2.8
M.Ed	95	3.7
Ph.D	13	0.6
Total	2550	100

More than 45% of the respondents revealed that teachers' qualification is a determinant of teachers' quality (TQ) and students' academic achievement (SAA) (Table 2). Students taught by more experienced teachers were most likely better in academic performance than their colleagues taught by less experienced teachers (Table 2, Figure 2). Most questionnaire items have higher mean scores than the weighted mean score, indicating how significance the measured variables were (Table 2).

Figure 1: Proportional sector showing the Teachers' qualifications in the study area between 2016-2018

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Table 2: Analysis of teachers' quality (TQ) assessment questionnaire administered to senior secondary teachers and heads

Question term	ML	L	U	MU	Mean Score
Teachers' Academic Qualifications					
All teachers in this school have academic qualifications to teach the students at senior secondary level.	60 (2.4%)	213 (8.4%)	1372 (53.8%)	905 (35.5%)	1.77
Teachers' academic qualifications influence the students' academic achievements.	1427 (56%)	993 (38.2%)	121 (4.7%)	9 (0.4%)	3.55
Teachers' academic qualifications are determinants of their quality.	1298 (50.9%)	1002 (39.3%)	229 (9.0%)	21 (0.8%)	3.49
Teachers' with first and/or higher degrees are more effective in the classroom.	826 (32.4%)	1190 (46.7%)	502 (19.7%)	32 (1.2%)	3.10
Excellent mastering of one's subject as a teacher is dependent on one's academic qualification.	871 (34.2%)	1234 (48.4%)	411 (16.1%)	34 (1.3%)	3.15
Teachers' Professional Qualifications					
Majority of teachers in this school have professional teaching and teachers' certifications.	164 (6.4%)	215 (8.4%)	1278 (50.2%)	893 (35.0%)	1.86
Teachers' with professional teaching qualification(s) have better teaching skills to impart knowledge to students.	408 (16.0%)	1063 (41.7%)	947 (37.1%)	132 (5.2%)	2.68
Teachers' with professional teaching qualification(s) have better students' assessment and evaluation skills.	692 (27.1%)	1245 (48.9%)	531 (20.8%)	82 (3.2%)	2.99
Teachers' with professional teaching qualification(s) keep better records of students and their performances.	320 (12.6%)	794 (31.1%)	1119 (43.9%)	317 (12.4%)	2.44
The quality of teachers in the school is a reflection of students' academic achievement.	1211 (47.4%)	910 (35.6%)	386 (15.3%)	43 (1.7%)	3.30
Teachers' Teaching Experiences					
Majority of teachers in this school have at least 5 years teaching experiences.	948 (37.2%)	977 (38.3%)	507 (19.9%)	118 (4.6%)	3.08
Teachers with at least 5 years experiences do better in disseminating knowledge to their students.	527 (20.7%)	951 (37.3%)	827 (32.4%)	245 (9.6%)	2.69
Teachers with more than 5 years teaching experiences have better knowledge and ability for students' control and class management.	375 (14.7%)	975 (38.2%)	929 (36.5%)	271 (10.6%)	2.57
Students taught by more experienced teachers perform academically better.	1096 (43%)	912 (35.8%)	403 (15.8%)	139 (5.4%)	3.16
Weighted Mean					2.85

Note: ML= most likely; L= likely; U= unlikely; MU= most unlikely.

The mean scores in **bold** are higher than the weighted mean score of **2.85**.

This subsequently reflected in the academic performance of their students with the public school having better results. These findings are explained in the context of the fact that teachers' academic qualifications have great influence on the quality of educational output (Olutola, 1999; Carroll et al., 2000; Ingersoll, 2001; Hanushek et al., 2004; Clotfelter et al., 2007). The implication of this is that teachers' mastery of subject-matter, knowledge of teaching methodology and the certification status of teachers have a strong positive relationship with SAA (Darling-Hammond, 2003; Darling-Hammond and Sykes, 2000). In a study conducted in New York City to find out high school students' performance in Mathematics and Science using data from the National Educational Longitudinal Studies of 1998 (NELS), it was discovered that fully certified teachers have a statistically significant positive impact on student test scores relative to teachers who are not certified in their subject area. This shows that schools can make a difference in students' learning and a substantial portion of that difference is attributable to teachers (Sanders and Rivers, 1996).

In contrast, a study conducted by some educationists in Edo South Senatorial District of Nigeria, revealed that teachers' quality and academic qualification had no significant influence on students' academic performance (Josiah and Oluwatoyin, 2017). Furthermore, Teachers' years of experiences were found to have significant influence on the SAA in our study. These findings were consistent with the findings of Awoyemi (2002) that a significant relationship exists between teachers' years of service and students' academic performance.

Table 3: Analysis of WASSCE results for 2016-2018 in the selected schools

Year	Public School					Private School				
	No. of students who sat for the exam	No. of students with 5 Credits and above including Maths & English	%	No. of students who failed	%	No. of students who sat for the exam	No. of students with 5 Credits and above including Maths & English	%	No. of students who failed	%
2016	2,658	664	25%	1,994	75%	417	80	19.20%	337	80.8%
2017	2,143	501	23.4%	1,642	76.6%	304	47	15.50%	257	84.5%
2018	2,709	563	20.8%	2,146	79.2%	321	41	12.80%	280	87.2%
Total	7,510	1,728		5,782		1,042	168		874	

Note: No. of students who failed = No. of students with 5 Credits and above including Maths & English.

Across the years of study, the SAA was lower in the private school relative to the public schools (Table 3). Twenty-three percent (23%) of the students who sat for the West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) in the sampled public schools during the 3 years of investigation passed with at least 5 Credits including Mathematics

and English language. Private school recorded only 16% of pass (Table 3). In general, the performance of the students was relatively poor especially in the private school. The finding was inconsistent with the report from WAEC (2016, 2017, 2018) that more than 20% of the total number of candidates that sat for the West African Senior Secondary Certificate examinations in those years passed with five credits including Mathematics and English (Josiah and Oluwatoyin, 2017). The discrepancies in the results might be attributed to the facts that most of the schools investigated in this present study were in the rural areas and while most schools are in the urban areas and with better WASSCE results. An Educationist has earlier attested that it is not uncommon to find students who have graduated in secondary schools showing very poor mastery of reading, writing and computational skills besides their terrible ignorance in the entire subjects that they have been taught for six years of secondary education (Sani 2006). According to Arinde (2010), it is rare nowadays to find secondary school students working hard to excel in their examinations, and this consequently leads to poor academic achievement.

Figure 2: Percentages of students with at least five credits passed in the subjects taught by teachers with the different levels of qualifications during the study period

Figure 3: Analysis showing the relationship between number (in %) of teachers' years of teaching experience and total number of students with 5 credits in the subject(s) taught by each teacher

The correlation between TQ and SAA was strong ($R^2 = 0.925$) (Figure 3). At 0.05 level of confidence, the regression analysis showed significant relationship between TQ and SAA ($p > 0.001$). Furthermore, more than 75% of the students taught by teachers with master's degrees and above had at least 5 credits between 2016-2018 in the study area (Figure 2). These findings revealed that teachers' quality had strong influence on the students' academic achievement. The higher the years of teaching experience and qualification, the higher the number of students who passed with at least 5 credits in various subjects taught by the teachers. Therefore, the hypothesis I of this study has been achieved by the rejection of the null hypotheses (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypotheses (H_1). This is because teachers' quality has a direct influence on the students' academic achievement as was also confirmed from the analysis of the respondents as shown in Table 2. This result was consistent with the work of Asuku (1999) that the quality of the product of any industry is reflective in the quality of the producing industry. This signifies that high-quality students, might have passed through an equally high-quality caliber of teachers. Having observed the importance of teachers' quality in the nation's educational system, the Federal Government of Nigeria passed a policy that teachers' education should be given a major priority in all educational planning because "no education system can rise above the quality of its teachers" (FRN, 2004).

4. Conclusions

The following conclusions were made based from the findings of the study:

- The public senior secondary school had better teacher quality than the private secondary schools in YSLGA, Ogun State, Nigeria. And the teachers' quality measured were teachers' academic qualification, professional qualification and years of teaching experience.
- The quality of teachers significantly influenced the academic achievement of students in secondary schools in YSLGA, Ogun State, Nigeria.
- The level of academic achievement of students in secondary schools in YSLGA, Ogun State was poor.

5. Implications

The result of this study showed that teachers' quality in secondary schools in YSLGA, Ogun State was average in the public schools but poor in the private schools, and these quality statuses were reflected in the students' academic achievement. This has implication for educational management because principals of schools as administrators must ensure proper supervision of teachers and harness their potentials for improved quality of students in schools. The result of this study revealed that the academic achievement of students was below average. To attain excellence in schools, the product of the institutions must be of high grade because the performance of teachers is based on the academic achievement of students. The school heads, the owners (government

and /or proprietors) have the responsibility of ensuring improved standard in their school.

6. Recommendations

- School heads should ensure that the potential of the teachers is well harnessed and utilized to reflect the true picture of their quality in the academic achievement of students.
- Teachers must wake up to their responsibilities and be dedicated to their subjects and duty in the classroom because poor performance of students will always be referred to their failure in their designated duties.
- Students must ensure they continue to be industrious to improve on their performance in the school to achieve a successful future for themselves.
- Government through the inspectorate division must routinely visit schools to ensure that teachers are qualified and are properly discharging their primary assignment.

Conflict of Interest Statement

There was no conflict of interest reported by the authors.

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References

- Adebayo F. A. (2007). Quantity and quality of teachers in public and private secondary schools, Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Management* 6 (1): 143-150.
- Arinde M. R. (2010). Educational Services, Teacher Quality and Students' Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools, North Central Zone, Nigeria. Unpublished Dissertation Thesis. Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education, University of Ilorin, Nigeria.
- Asuku I. B. (1999). Relationship of teachers' personal variables with their job performance and students' academic achievement in Kogi State secondary schools. Unpublished PhD thesis, University of Ibadan, Nigeria.
- Awoyemi M. A. (2002). Measuring the effective teacher: problems and prospect. *Journal of Teacher Education. University of Ile-Ife* 20 (1): 90-93.
- Carroll S., Reichardt R., Guarino C., (2000). The distribution of teachers among California's school districts and schools. Santa Monica, CA: RAND Corporation.

- Clotfelter C. T, Ladd H. F, Vigdor J. L., & Wheeler J. (2007). High-poverty schools and the distribution of teachers and principals. CALDER Working Paper 1. Washington, DC: The Urban Institute.
- Darling-Hammond L. (2000). Teacher quality and student achievement: A review of state policy evidence. *Education Policy Analysis Archives* 8(1). Available: <http://epaa.asu.edu/epaa/v8n1>
- Darling-Hammond L., Sykes G., (2003). Wanted: A national teacher supply policy for education: The right way to meet the "Highly Qualified Teacher" challenge. *Education Policy Analysis Archives* 11(33). <http://epaa.asu.edu/epaa/v11n33/>.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). National policy on education. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Hanushek E., Kain J., Rivkin S. (2004). Why public schools lose teachers. *Journal of Human Resources* 39(2): 326-54.
- Ingersoll R. (2001). Teacher turnover and teacher shortages: An organizational analysis. *American Educational Research Journal* 38(3): 499-534.
- Josiah O., Oluwatoyin K. B. (2017). Teacher Quality as Determinant of Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Edo South Senatorial District of Nigeria. *British Journal of Education* 5:19-30.
- Madumere-Obike C. U. (2003). Managing quality assurance: the secondary education sector. A paper presented at the 18th annual congress of the Nigerian Academy of Education at University of Port Harcourt, 10th – 15th November.
- Nwogbo V. N. (2007). Ways to promote quality instruction in secondary schools in Anambra State. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Management* 6 (1): 105-120.
- Nworgu G. G. (1991). Educational research: basic issues and methodology. Owerri: Wisdom Pub.
- Obemeata J. O. (1996). Education in the service of humanity. The Education study and Research Group Ibadan.
- Olutola S. A. (1999). Teacher quality and internal efficiency. Unpublished Ph.D thesis, University of Ibadan.
- Sanders M., Rivers C., (1996). Statewide class-size Studies. Prime Time and Star, Tennessee Project Star: Dallas, Texas.
- Sanders W. L., Wright S. P., Horn S. P. (1997). Teacher and Classroom Context Effects on Student Achievement: Implications for Teacher Evaluation. *Journal of Personnel Evaluation in Education* 11: 57. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1007999204543>
- Sani D. M. (2006). Influence of school plant construction, utilization and maintenance on school effectiveness in Kebbi state secondary schools. An unpublished Ph.D. thesis. University of Ilorin.
- Zimbardo P. G. (1997). A passion for psychology: Teaching it charismatically, integrating teaching and research synergistically, and writing about it engagingly. In R. J. Sternberg (Ed.), *Teaching Introductory Psychology: Survival Tips from the Experts*. (pp. 7-34). Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.

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